

SYNTHESIS OF COUMARINS FROM *o*-HYDROXY-ARYL ALKYL
KETONES. PART V. FORMATION OF COUMARINS
FROM *o*-HYDROXYPHENYLBENZYL KETONES

BY DUHKHAHARAN CHAKRAVARTI AND BANKIM CHANDRA BERA

5-Methyl-, 5-chloro-, 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-methoxyphenylbenzyl ketones have been condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and ethyl α -bromopropionate under Reformatsky's condition to give hydroxy-esters which on dehydration and demethylation yield coumarin derivatives in quantitative yields.

The *o*-hydroxy-aryl alkyl ketones have been conveniently used by Chakravarti *et al* (Chakravarti and Mazumdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 136; Chakravarti and Datta, *ibid.*, 1940, **17**, 65) for the synthesis of coumarin derivatives. The present investigation has been undertaken to study the applicability of this synthetical method starting with *o*-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketones.

The ketones *e.g.*, 5 methyl-2-methoxy-, 5-chloro-2-methoxy- and 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-methoxyphenyl benzyl ketones have been condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and with ethyl α -bromopropionate forming hydroxy-esters, which have been treated with thionyl chloride and pyridine to yield unsaturated esters. These unsaturated esters on being treated with hydriodic acid yield coumarins quantitatively.

Ketones used.		Halogenated fatty esters.	Coumarins obtained.
5-Methyl-2-methoxyphenyl ketone	benzyl	Ethyl bromoacetate	4-Benzyl-6-methylcoumarin
Do		Ethyl α -bromopropionate	3:6-Dimethyl-4-benzylcoumarin
5-Chloro-2-methoxyphenyl ketone	benzyl	Ethyl bromoacetate	4-Benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin
Do		Ethyl α -bromopropionate	3-Methyl-4-benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin
3-Chloro-5-methyl-2-methoxyphenyl benzyl ketone		Ethyl bromoacetate	4-Benzyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin
Do		Ethyl α -bromopropionate	3:6-Dimethyl-4-benzyl-8-chloro- coumarin

E X P E R I M E N T A L

*Preparation of 4-Benzyl-6-methylcoumarin and 3:6-Dimethyl-4-benzylcoumarin from
5-Methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl benzyl Ketone.*

5-Methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone was prepared from the phenylacetate of *p*-cresol (20 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g.). The mixture was heated to 130-35° in absence of moisture for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The glassy mass was decomposed with ice-cold hydrochloric acid and it was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was washed with sodium carbonate solution and water. It was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether distilled off and the product distilled at 195-99°/6 mm. as a colourless oily liquid which on standing solidified to colourless crystals, m.p. 63°, yield 16 g. It is identical with the compound prepared by Auwers (*Ber.*, 1920, **53**, 2277) from *p*-cresol methyl ether and phenylacetyl chloride.

5-Methyl-2-methoxyphenyl benzyl ketone was obtained by the methylation of the above ketone with methyl iodide in alcoholic sodium ethoxide solution. It distilled at 193°/2 mm. as a colourless thick oil. The methyl ether has been described by Auwers (*loc. cit.*) to boil at 205-207°/14 mm.

Ethyl 5-Methyl-2-methoxy-β-benzyl Cinnamate.—A mixture of 5-methyl-2-methoxyphenyl benzyl ketone (7 g.), freshly distilled ethyl bromoacetate (10 g.), zinc wool (5 g.) and dry benzene (50 c.c.) was heated on a boiling water-bath for about 2 hours, when the zinc dissolved. After cooling the solution was poured into ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid solution. The benzene layer was separated, washed with dilute sodium carbonate and then with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removing benzene the hydroxy-ester was distilled at 215-20°/3 mm. as a light brown oil. The hydroxy-ester was converted into the unsaturated ester with thionyl chloride in presence of dry pyridine in dry ice-cold ethereal solution in the usual manner. It was distilled at 200-205°/3 mm. as a thick brown oil, which solidified on keeping for a few days. (Found: C, 77·64; H, 6·86. C₂₀H₂₂O₃ requires C, 77·42; H, 7·09 per cent).

4-Benzyl-6 methylcoumarin was obtained by demethylation of the above unsaturated ester with hydriodic acid (sp. gr. 1·7) for 2 hours. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol as brilliant colourless crystals, m.p. 148°. (Found: C, 81·24; H, 5·60. C₁₇H₁₄O₂ requires C, 81·60; H, 5·60 per cent). The same coumarin was smoothly obtained from the ethoxy derivative of 5-methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone.

5-Methyl-2-ethoxyphenyl benzyl ketone was prepared in the usual way from 5-methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone by heating with ethyl iodide in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide solution. It distilled at 200-201°/5 mm. as a yellow oil. (Found: C, 80·04; H, 7·35. C₁₇H₁₈O₂ requires C, 80·32; H, 7·09 per cent). Ethyl 2-ethoxy-5-methyl-β-benzyl cinnamate was obtained by dehydration with thionyl chloride and pyridine of the unsaturated ester, prepared by the condensation of 5-methyl-2-ethoxyphenyl benzyl ketone and ethyl bromoacetate in the presence of zinc wool. It distilled at 210-15°/5 mm. as a deep brown oil. (Found: C, 77·40; H, 7·22. C₂₁H₂₄O₃ requires C, 77·78; H, 7·41 per cent). 4-Benzyl-6-methylcoumarin was obtained from the above unsaturated ester by heating with hydriodic acid as usual, m.p. 148° (mixed m.p. with the compound prepared above).

3:6-Dimethyl-4-benzylcoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-α:5-dimethyl-α-β-benzyl cinnamate was obtained by the dehydration with thionyl chloride and pyridine of the unsaturated ester, prepared by the condensation of 2-methoxy-5-methyl benzyl ketone with ethyl α-bromopropionate in the presence of zinc wool. It distilled at 203°/2·5 mm. as a thick brown viscous liquid, which did not solidify on cooling. (Found: C, 77·76; H, 7·47. C₂₁H₂₄O₃ requires C, 77·78; H, 7·41 per cent). Demethylation of the above unsaturated ester gave 3:6-dimethyl-4-benzylcoumarin, which crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless shining needles, m.p. 136°. (Found: C, 81·74; H, 6·04. C₁₈H₁₆O₂ requires C, 81·82; H, 6·06 per cent).

Preparation of 4-Benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin and 3-Methyl-4-benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin from 2-Hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl benzyl Ketone.

2-Methoxy-5-chlorophenyl benzyl ketone was obtained by the methylation with methyl iodide in alcoholic sodium ethoxide solution of 2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenyl benzyl ketone, prepared from 4-chlorophenyl methyl ether and phenylacetyl chloride according to the method of Wittig (*Annalen*, 1925, 446, 169). Attempts to prepare 2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenylbenzyl ketone from the phenyl acetate of *p*-chlorophenol by Fries' rearrangement were unsuccessful.

4-Benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-5-chloro- β -benzylcinnamate prepared the reaction of 2-methoxy-5-chlorophenyl benzyl ketone and ethyl bromoacetate and the subsequent dehydration of the unsaturated ester with thionyl chloride and pyridine in the usual manner, distilled at 208°/4 mm. as a pale brown thick oil. (Found: Cl, 11.13. $C_{18}H_{19}O_3$ Cl requires Cl, 10.74 per cent). The unsaturated ester on heating with hydriodic acid gave 4-benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin. It crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless crystals, m.p. 101°. (Found: Cl, 12.99. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 13.12 per cent).

3-Methyl-4-benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-5-chloro- α -methyl- β -benzyl cinnamate was prepared by the condensation of 2-methoxy-5-chlorophenyl benzyl ketone and ethyl α -bromopropionate in the presence of zinc wool and subsequent dehydration of the hydroxy-ester with thionyl chloride and pyridine in the usual manner. It distilled at 212°/2 mm. as a yellow oil. (Found: Cl, 10.32. $C_{20}H_{21}O_3$ Cl requires Cl, 10.30 per cent). The unsaturated ester on demethylation with hydriodic acid gave 3-methyl-4-benzyl-6-chlorocoumarin, which crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles, m.p. 162°. (Found: Cl, 12.43. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 12.48 per cent).

Preparation of 4-Benzyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin and 3:6-Dimethyl-4-benzyl-8-chlorocoumarin from 2-Hydroxy-3-chloro-5-methylphenyl benzyl Ketone.

3-Chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone was prepared by means of Fries' reaction on 2-chloro-4-methylphenyl acetate (pale yellow oil, b.p. 201°/6.5 mm.) obtained by condensing 2-chloro-4-methylphenol (Mazzara and Lumbuti, *Gazzetta*, 1896, 26, 399) with equimolecular proportion of phenylacetyl chloride. It was obtained as light yellow needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 68.68; H, 4.80. $C_{15}H_{13}O_2$ Cl requires C, 69.09; H, 4.99 per cent).

3-Chloro-5-methyl-2-methoxyphenyl benzyl ketone, prepared as usual from 3-chloro-5-methyl-2-hydroxyphenyl benzyl ketone with methyl iodide in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide solution, distilled at 195-200°/3.5 mm. as a light yellow oil. (Found: Cl, 12.96. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 12.93 per cent).

4-Benzyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methyl- β -benzyl cinnamate was obtained by the condensation of 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methylphenyl benzyl ketone and ethyl bromoacetate in the presence of zinc wool and subsequent dehydration of the hydroxy-ester with thionyl chloride and pyridine. It distilled at 210-15°/4.5 mm. as a very thick brown oil. (Found: Cl, 10.16. $C_{20}H_{21}O_3$ Cl requires Cl, 10.30 per cent). *4-Benzyl-6-methyl-8-chlorocoumarin* was obtained by the demethylation of this unsaturated ester with hydriodic acid. It crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless shining needles, m.p. 161°. (Found: Cl, 12.50. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 12.48 per cent).

3:6-Dimethyl-4-benzyl-8-chlorocoumarin.—Ethyl 2-methoxy-3-chloro- α :5-dimethyl- β -benzyl cinnamate was prepared by the condensation of 2-methoxy-3-chloro-5-methylphenyl benzyl ketone and ethyl α -bromo-propionate in the presence of zinc wool and the subsequent dehydration of the hydroxy-ester with thionyl chloride as usual. It distilled at 210°/2 mm as a pale yellow liquid. (Found: Cl, 9.76. $C_{21}H_{23}O_3$ Cl requires Cl, 9.90 per cent). The unsaturated ester on demethylation with hydriodic acid gave 3:6-dimethyl-4-benzyl-8-chlorocoumarin, which crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless shining needles, m.p. 173° (Found: Cl, 11.89. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 11.89 per cent).